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**Assessment of the Integrated Power Turbine (IPT),
a Homemade Wind Turbine Model
for Renewable Energy Sources**

**A
Project Report**
for the Fulfillment of
the Requirements in
**English for Academic
and Professional Purposes
(EAPP)**

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12 – STEM Archimedes

February 2021

Assessment of the Integrated Power Turbine (IPT), a Homemade Wind Turbine Model for Renewable Energy Sources

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INTRODUCTION

Purpose

This project report assesses the Integrated Power Turbine (IPT), a homemade wind turbine model as a small-scale power source that can produce electricity on its own.

Problem

While the topology of the country makes it suitable for harnessing renewable energies such as solar energy, hydrothermal energy, hydropower, wave power, and wind energy, the Philippines is still mainly relying on coal-based energy sources according to Fitch Solutions. In their report, coal is said to account for 59% of the Philippines' energy mix by 2029, up from 29.1% as of 2019 based on latest energy department data.

Scope

The following assessment of the homemade wind turbine model only simulates its usage on a simple parallel circuit with the turbine as the power source for the light emitting diodes (LED's). Moreover, the report cannot record the voltage of the wind turbine that it produces due to the lack of a multimeter.

BACKGROUND

Theory

A wind turbine converts wind energy to electricity using the aerodynamic force from the rotor blades. Air pressure on one side of the blade decreases when the wind blows on it, thus creating a difference in air pressure which causes lift and drag. The force of the lift is stronger than the drag and this causes the rotor to spin. The rotor connects to the generator, either directly like in direct drive turbines or through a shaft and a gearbox that speed up the rotation and allow for electricity to pass along a smaller generator. The said conversion of aerodynamic force to the rotation of a generator creates electricity.

Research

By typing the phrase “wind turbines” on the search directory of the popular research directory ScienceDirect, there are 65,860 results that will pop up. In another case from another directory, Academia.edu, searching the same phrase will collect 56,476 results in their advanced search and 1,285 results in their basic search. The collected search results include the efficacy of wind turbines in certain locations in the world, technical review papers on the formation and deployment of these turbines, and papers that publish the structural design and analysis of state-of-the-art turbines.

Hypothesis

This report incorporates a two-tailed test wherein the IPT is subject to functionality. The hypotheses that will be used for this report are stated below:

H_0 : The homemade wind turbine project is functional but didn't meet the required conditions in order to power up a commercial light emitting diode (LED).

H_a : The homemade wind turbine project is functional and met the required conditions in order to power up a commercial light emitting diode (LED).

TEST AND EVALUATION

Apparatus

The design for the homemade wind turbine model is a representation of a horizontal-axis turbine, with the said model containing four plastic bottle “blades” and operates with the turbine pivoting at the top of the supporting tower so the blades face into the wind source.

The model is built with the following materials:

- 6V DC motor
- Light emitting diode (LED) lights
- Jumper wires & alligator clips
- Breadboard (full size, 56 x 65)
- Carton pizza box
- 1.5 L polyethylene terephthalate (PET) bottle
- Glue sticks & gun
- White glue
- Scissors
- Compass
- Ruler
- Electrical tape
- Stick
- Bottle cap

Figures 1 – 2: The materials used for the Integrate Power Turbine (IPT).

The model will be supported by a supporting tower made from the carton pizza box and the neck of the PET bottle. The DC motor is placed on the top of the tower along with parts of the PET bottle to be used as the blades of the turbine. This set-up will be connected by jumper wires that are also connected to a simple breadboard placement of commercial LED's.

Build Process Flowchart

The flowchart is followed to check upon the Integrated Power Turbine (IPT) in its functionality as a homemade wind turbine model. This will serve as the backbone of the system and the basis when assembling the product and testing it.

Image Flowchart

Title of Project:
Integrated Power Turbine (IPT)

Members:
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- 1

CREATION OF THE TURBINE BLADES

- 2

CREATION OF THE SUPPORT TOWER

- 3

ATTACHMENT OF BLADES TO DC MOTOR

- 4

LINKING TO LIGHTING SET-UP

- 5

FINAL OUTPUT OF IPT

Figure 3: The build process model that will be followed for the creation of the Integrated Power Turbine (IPT).

Illustration by: Marc Andrie M. Bermundo
Photos by: Mark Jonel V. Abad

FINDINGS

Testing Phase

During the testing stage of the turbine, the apparatus operated with the exertion of mechanical force to the motor that was done in a counterclockwise motion. However, the illumination of the LED in this set-up is intermittent as the sudden surge of voltage was only caused by the abrupt action of mechanical force into the motor.

Figure 3: The building process for the Integrated Power Turbine (IPT).

Trials Phase

In the trials phase, an electric fan was utilized to simulate the wind in order for the blades of the model turbine to move. Unfortunately, the wind force sustained by the IPT was not able to generate enough voltage to light up the LED light through the support of a reused DC motor.

Figure 4: Trial by hand of the Integrated Power Turbine (IPT).

Figure 5: Testing of the Integrated Power Turbine (IPT) using an electric fan to simulate the wind.

INTERPRETATION

Possible causes of the turbine not working is because the speed and pressure caught by the model is not enough, leading to a lack in voltage generation to light up the LED. A supporting technical aspect involved in this is due to the generation of the DC motor not being suitable to power up a LED light in a wind turbine set-up.

Another causation would be that the spin of the blades is clockwise, which means that there is a possibility that the blades work on a counterclockwise motion rather than clockwise.

Technicalities that also affected this report is due to the lack of resources and the duration of the project.

CONCLUSION

This report settles that a homemade wind turbine model can be functional for generating electricity and powering up electrical devices. Yet, this report also concluded that in building a wind turbine model, the resources that are used is opted out to produce electricity, as it turns out that this report supported the null hypothesis in the two-tailed test. The null hypothesis used in this report stated that “the homemade wind turbine project is functional but didn’t meet the required conditions in order to power up a commercial light emitting diode (LED)”.

SOURCES

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LABORATORY AND PROJECT REPORT CHECKLIST

- Have I clearly defined the purpose of this report?
- Have I clearly described the problem that requires this report?
- Have I clearly explained the limitations of this report?
- Have I discussed any theory necessary for the reader to understand the report?
- Have I reviewed relevant prior research?
- Have I described the apparatus I used to collect the data?
- Have I described the procedure I used to collect the data?
- Have I clearly provided the results of the test?
- Have I properly interpreted these results?
- Have I made proper conclusions from these interpretations?
- Have I made a recommendation based on my conclusions?

SOURCE: Pocket Book of Technical Writing for Engineers and Scientists by Leo Finkelstein, Jr.